

Adhesion and Corrosion Issues Associated with Non-Conductive Ceramic (NCC) Coatings

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Abstract— During the past two decades, non-conductive ceramic (NCC) coatings have been widely applied to connectors to prevent cathodic delamination. The ceramic comprising the NCC coating cannot support the electrochemical reactions (such as the reduction of dissolved oxygen to produce hydroxyl ions) that normally cause adhesive bonds to fail under cathodic delamination conditions. While the wide-scale adoption of this technology initially reduced the number and frequency of cable connector debonding failures, an upsurge in cable failures over the last five years has revealed that NCC coatings, as originally designed and implemented, are now much less effective in preventing cathodic delamination. Standard NCC-coated connectors now fail rapidly under cathodic delamination conditions rather than lasting the 10-15 years projected by accelerated life testing results obtained when NCC coatings were first being evaluated. Many recent cable connector failures have been traced to debonds between the NCC coating and the primers used to adhere polyurethane encapsulants to the connectors. While the exact mechanism via which these debonds occur has not yet been definitively established, deterioration of the NCC coating's "seal-coat" layer under the localized highly alkaline conditions that develop during cathodic delamination is believed to play a critical role in the debonding process. Corrosion-based failures of NCC coatings applied to connectors not subjected to cathodic delamination conditions have also been observed. These failures tend to be restricted to connector backshells made from highly corrosion-resistant metals/alloys (e.g., titanium, iniconel etc.) and result from dissimilar metals or metal alloys being in contact with each other in seawater - thereby initiating and sustaining a galvanic corrosion cell. The end result of the process is the dissolution of the NCC coating's "metal matching layer", which undermines the NCC layer and causes it to debond from the connector backshell. Examples of the above debonding scenarios obtained from autopsies of failed cables will be used to emphasize the need for new/improved technologies for preventing the cathodic disbondment of cable connector backshells from their overmolding encapsulants.

Keywords—cathodic delamination, cathodic disbondment, cable connectors, NCC, non-conductive ceramic coatings, accelerated life testing, adhesion, galvanic corrosion

I. INTRODUCTION

The hulls and outboard machinery of most marine vessels require some form of cathodic protection (either sacrificial anodes or an induced current cathodic protection - ICCP -

system) to prevent corrosion damage. While these systems prevent metal in contact with seawater from corroding, an unfortunate side-effect of their use is the destruction of metal to polymer bonds via a process referred to as "cathodic delamination" or "cathodic disbondment". Hardware not directly connected to the cathodic protection system itself can become cathodically polarized when connected (directly or indirectly) to a protected hull. Cathodic delamination is believed to cause hundreds of millions of dollars of damage to marine hardware every year.

Cathodic delamination is known to cause paint to debond from metal hull surfaces, and polymeric encapsulants to debond from metal surfaces on specialized pieces of hardware (e.g., sensors and connectors). The process was recognized over 80 years ago [1] as a cause for paint debonding from steel. The key chemical reaction during the cathodic disbondment of a polymer from a cathodically polarized metal substrate is the reduction of dissolved oxygen in water to generate hydroxyl an ions [2, 3]:

The reduction of oxygen is the major cathodic reaction that occurs when the cathodic polarization of the metal substrate is below -1000 mV versus the saturated Calomel electrode (SCE). The electrons in the reaction are generated at sacrificial anodes or at an ICCP system anode. The hydroxyl ions are generated at the metal-polymer interface where they create an extremely alkaline/high pH environment that weakens and degrades most metal-to-polymer bonds, eventually causing their failure.

One way to prevent cathodic disbondment would be to bond the polymeric substrate to a non-electrically conductive surface. Non-electrically conductive surfaces cannot support equation (1) because they prevent the electrons required by the reaction from reaching the region where the polymer is bonded to the substrate. Of course, the non-electrically conductive surface itself would need to be firmly attached to any underlying metal substrate. During the 1990s as a part of a U.S. Navy financed Small Business Innovative Research (SBIR) initiative, a company called Texas Research

Institute-Austin (TRI-Austin) developed a method for bonding flame-sprayed ceramic coatings onto metal surfaces subject to cathodic polarization. The resulting product, sold to both military and civilian customers, was called “Bond-Coat” by TRI-Austin, but became better known by its generic name, “non-conductive ceramic coating” or just “NCC coating” (figure 1). The NCC layer itself is not sprayed directly onto the metal comprising the connector backshell. Instead, a ‘metal interface layer’ or ‘bond-coat layer’ is sprayed first directly onto the connector backshell. This initial layer is between 50 to 75 microns thick and it is usually composed of the same metal as the backshell itself. The metal interface layer creates a rough surface to which the NCC layer is bonded. The NCC layer is a ceramic composed primarily of aluminum oxide and titanium oxide. It is about 200 microns thick and, because of the spraying process, it is somewhat porous. To seal the porosity, a “seal-coat layer” is applied over the NCC layer. The seal coat is typically a phenolic resin (e.g., MetcoSeal AP) although other materials, such as epoxies, have also been used (e.g., Chemlok 219). On top of the seal coat layer the standard Cytec or PRC-DeSoto primer/polyurethane encapsulant systems are applied.

Fig. 1. Drawing of a typical “NCC coating.” The thickness of the metal interface layer plus the NCC layer plus the seal coat layer is approximately 250 microns.

NCC coatings were first applied to connector backshells during the late 1990s. Soon thereafter, the number of cable failures dropped considerably. Over the last five years, however, the failure rates for outboard cables, even those with NCC coatings applied, have increased significantly. The reasons why the use of NCC-coated connectors no longer guarantees a long service lifetime under cathodic delamination conditions has not been definitively established. Our laboratory at the Naval Undersea Warfare Center (NUWC)

Division Newport was asked to autopsy failed fiber optic outboard cables during 2011. Because these particular cables had NCC-coated connectors at both ends, it was hoped that a thorough, scientific dissection of their connectors would provide some insight into why NCC-coatings had become undependable. This paper highlights some of the key findings of our investigation into the causes of failure for these cables.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

A. Samples

Four failed fiber optic cables were provided for analysis. The cables had been in use for approximately five years. One end of the cable connected to a sensor that was electrically isolated from the hull of the submarine to which it was attached. The connector backshell at this end of the cable was composed of Inconel 625 alloy and it mated with a titanium receptacle on the sensor. These connectors had Inconel nut that were very clean when received – there was no evidence of any “calcareous”/carbonate deposits on the nut or on any of the exposed metal surfaces of the connector. The opposite end of the cable connected to the hull of the parent submarine. The connector backshell at this end of the cable was composed of K-monel and it mated to a K-monel receptacle attached to the hull. The nuts for these connectors were composed of brass, and they (along with all exposed metal surfaces on the connector) were heavily coated with “calcareous”/carbonate deposits (the deposits fizzed vigorously when exposed to a dilute acid solution). The cable jacket was a polychloroprene formulation.

Both connectors on each cable were overmolded with the PRC-Desoto primer and polyurethane (PR-420 primer and PR-1547 amber polyurethane) encapsulant system. When cut in half using a band saw, the interiors of all of the connectors exhibited evidence of having been flooded with seawater. The polyurethane overmolds on all of the connectors were cut into strips of polyurethane for peel-testing by means of a cutting bit attached to a variable speed Dremel tool. The polyurethane was removed down to the NCC coating so that the peel strength between the polyurethane and the NCC coating could be determined.

B. Materials

Our experiments to duplicate the observed bonding failures used both Inconel 625 and monel 400 alloy coupons as the metal substrates. Monel 400 was used in place of K-monel because it is similar in chemical composition and (unlike K-monel) it is readily available in flat bar stock from metal suppliers. The Inconel and monel 400 flat-bar stock was machined into rectangular coupons 4 x 1 x 0.25 inches in size. A small threaded hole was made on the flat sides of each coupon opposite the bonding surface for the attachment of sacrificial zinc anodes for those samples that would be subjected to cathodic debonding conditions during their accelerated life test (ALT).

Some of the Inconel and monel coupons were oversprayed with the “standard” NCC coating system in accordance with the prevailing Navy guidance. The seal coat layer used for all of the NCC-coated coupons was MetcoSeal AP. The metal matching layer applied to both sets of coupons was Eutectic 21021 (primarily a nickel alloy with small amounts of aluminum and molybdenum). The PRC-DeSoto encapsulation system (PR-420 primer and PR-1547 polyurethane) was used exclusively to overmold the sample coupons.

For the cathodic delamination experiments, the samples were immersed in an elevated temperature salt solution (3.5% sodium chloride by weight). The zinc anodes attached to some samples were standard zinc boat rudder anodes (slightly “domed”, disc-like shapes approximately 1.5 inches in diameter and 0.25 inches thick at the top of the “dome”).

C. Sample Manufacture

The center two square inches of some of the Inconel coupons were sandblasted with 80 grit aluminum oxide and then rinsed/cleaned with acetone prior to primer being applied directly to their bonding surfaces. The other Inconel and monel 400 coupons were coated with the “standard” NCC coating and seal coat.

All samples first had their bonding surfaces painted with PR-420 primer. The PR-420 primer was allowed to air-dry for 2-4 hours before the samples were placed into a specially-designed metal mold (that made nine samples at a time) and then the PR-1547 (amber) polyurethane was applied. Pre-mixed and frozen PR-1547 was used to make all of the samples. The samples were then heated at 80°C for a minimum of 16 hours to cure the polyurethane.

Once the polyurethane had cured, the samples were removed from the metal mold, cut apart using a band-saw, and their edges were sanded flush so that no primer or polyurethane extended over the edges. A small hole was drilled into the polyurethane “tail” of the samples to allow them to be suspended from a metal bar attached to an acrylic rack used to hold them upright in the salt water filled ALT tank. Samples that were going to be exposed to cathodic delamination conditions had small zinc sacrificial anodes attached to their backsides (via a nylon screw) before they were placed into the holder racks; figures 2 and 3). These samples are referred to as “peel samples” because their ultimate fate, after environmental conditioning, was to be peeled to destruction on an Instron machine.

Fig. 2. Peel sample ready for testing. This sample has a sacrificial zinc anode attached to its backside. Only the center two square inches of the sample are bonded together.

Fig. 3. A set of twelve individual peel samples hung by their tails from metal rods fitted into slots on top of the acrylic holder-racks, before immersion in a salt water test tank.

D. Experimental Procedures

Conditioning of the peel test samples was conducted at 66°C in a 3.5% (by weight) NaCl solution. Every other day, pure oxygen gas was bubbled into the salt solution tanks to maintain their dissolved oxygen content. Three samples that were never subjected to the ALT conditioning were peel-tested in accordance with reference [4] to serve as baseline values for the peel strength of the various samples placed in the ALT. At various pre-selected time intervals, samples were removed from the test racks and pulled to failure on an Instron machine in accordance with reference [4]. The average peel strength and failure mode for each sample were recorded.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Examination of Failed Connectors

The lack of calcareous/carbonate deposits on the nuts and other exposed metal surfaces of the Inconel-backshell, “sensor-end” connectors verified that they had not been exposed to cathodic delamination conditions (such conditions generate a very high pH environment that causes carbonates to precipitate from seawater). Examination of the Inconel connector backshells indicated that the alloy chosen (inconel 625) was galvanically compatible with the titanium alloy on the sensor receptacles, because no evidence of corrosion, galvanic or otherwise, was found on the portions of the connector and sensor receptacle that were in direct contact with each other.

Peel testing of the polyurethane strips machined into the connector encapsulant indicated very poor adhesion between the backshells and the encapsulant. Examination of the peel strips once they had been pulled off of the backshells revealed that the NCC coating itself had debonded from the rest of the metal backshell. From visual observations alone, it was impossible to determine if the ceramic layer had debonded from the metal matching layer, or if the metal matching layer had debonded from the backshell (figure 4).

Fig. 4. Autopsied Inconel backshell connector showing: (a) NCC debonded from the backshell after peel testing (NCC coating is the black colored layer in the photo) and (b) clean appearance of the connector nut and exposed metal surfaces (no calcareous or carbonate deposits).

The monel backshell “hull-end” connectors appeared and behaved differently from the inconel backshell end. First, the connector nuts and exposed metal surfaces at this end of the cable were covered with calcareous/carbonate deposits – an indication that this end of the cable was exposed to cathodic delamination conditions. This is consistent with this end of the cable being attached to the hull of the parent vessel, which was cathodically protected by an ICCP system.

Peel testing of the polyurethane encapsulant bonds to these connector backshells again revealed poor adhesion. This time, however, the debonds occurred at the NCC coating – polyurethane primer interface. The NCC layer was intact and remained attached to the monel backshell, but the PR-420 primer was not well bonded to the NCC layer (figure 5).

Fig. 5. Autopsied monel backshell connector showing: (a) PR-420 primer debonded from the NCC layer after peel testing (NCC coating is the black colored layer in the photo) and (b) calcareous and/or carbonate deposits on the connector nut and exposed metal surfaces of the connector, indicating it was subjected to an environment conducive to cathodic delamination.

B. Experiments with Inconel Test Coupons

An attempt was made to re-create the sensor end connector failures under laboratory conditions using standard, ASTM D-429 peel samples. Inconel 625 coupons coated with the “standard” NCC coating, primed with PR-420 and overmolded with PR-1547 polyurethane were immersed in a 3.5% NaCl

solution maintained at 66°C. No zincs were attached to these samples because in real life, the Inconel backshell connectors that failed were not exposed to any cathodic voltage or currents.

After 8-10 weeks had passed, some of the samples were pulled from the ALT and peeled on an Instron machine. Prior to peeling, examination of the exposed edges of the samples indicated corrosion was occurring between the Inconel coupon and the PU-1547 overmold. The corrosion appeared to be centered on the NCC coating layer (figure 6).

Fig. 6. View of the exposed edge (bondline) of one of the NCC-coated inconel samples. The silver material is the inconel coupon, and the yellow/brown material is the PR-1547 polyurethane overmold. The dark spots are areas of corrosion residue centered on the NCC coating layer.

Examination of peeled samples indicated that the major failure mode was adhesive between the PR-420 primer and the PR-1547 polyurethane. However, on all samples, small areas of PR-420 primer also debonded from the NCC layer, starting from the exposed edges of the coupon and moving towards the interior of the sample. In a few areas, small pieces of the NCC coating had debonded from the inconel coupon and remained attached to the PR-1547 polyurethane substrate (figure 7).

Fig. 7. Peeled Inconel-NCC sample. Dark spots along the edges are regions where the PR-420 primer has debonded from the NCC layer. The red arrow is pointing to a piece of NCC that debonded from the inconel coupon during peel testing.

The laboratory ALT duplicated the bonding failure seen in the “sensor-end” cable connectors. The problem appeared to result from a corrosion reaction occurring where the NCC layer contacted the Inconel. In a salt water environment, Inconel behaves in a noble manner and is capable of participating in a galvanic corrosion cell with many other metals that are located farther down the galvanic series (i.e., more anodic). Suspicion immediately turned to the metal interface layer that is sprayed over the connector backshell to improve adhesion of the NCC layer to the backshell. Inconel alloys are a curious case, because there is no official guidance as to what the elemental composition of the metal interface layer should be. The records of the NCC applicator were examined and it was determined that a nickel aluminum molybdenum alloy designated “Eutectic

21021” was used on the Inconel backshells as part of the NCC coating application process for these connectors.

Samples were cut from some of the failed Inconel connectors and subjected to SEM/EDS analysis to: (a) verify the elemental composition of the metal interface layer used on these connectors; and (b) examine the bond line between the metal interface layer and the inconel for evidence of a corrosion reaction occurring between the two alloys. SEM/EDS analysis of the metal interface layer verified that it was composed of a nickel-aluminum-molybdenum alloy. SEM images of the region where the NCC coating and the Inconel came into contact with each other revealed that most of the metal interface layer that should have been located between the Inconel and the NCC layer had been dissolved away (figure 8).

Fig. 8. SEM image (1600x) of the interface region between the NCC coating (dark material making up the bottom half of the image) and the Inconel backshell of a failed connector (light gray material making up the top half of the image). A void exists between the two materials where the Eutectic 21021 “metal interface layer” was located.

The sensor end of the failed cables was electrically isolated from the vessel hull and thus was not cathodically polarized. Thus, the use of NCC coatings on these connectors was not necessary, because NCC coatings were developed specifically to prevent cathodic delamination. To explore this possibility further, standard ASTM-D-429 peel samples were made using Inconel 625 coupons. These coupons were sandblasted and then primed with PR-420 and overmolded with PR-1547 (no NCC coatings were applied). These coupons were placed into the 66°C salt water ALT bath. The samples were not connected to sacrificial zinc anodes.

Three samples were removed from the ALT and subjected to peel testing every two weeks. Even after 16 weeks had passed, no debonds occurred with these samples and their average peel strength values had not significantly declined from the initial values.

C. Experiments with Monel Test Coupons

An effort was also made to re-create the failures that occurred on the “hull-end” of the failed cables. Standard ASTM D-429 peel samples were made using monel 400 as the metal substrate. “Standard” NCC coatings were applied to these coupons, after which they were primed with PR-420

primer and then overmolded with PR-1547 polyurethane. The finished coupons were immersed in the 66°C salt water ALT bath. Small sacrificial zinc anodes were attached to each sample to ensure the monel coupons were cathodically polarized. The use of the anodes simulated the cathodic voltage and current the real connectors would have picked up from being attached to the cathodically protected hull of the parent vessel.

Samples made in the above manner but not exposed to salt water under cathodic delamination conditions routinely exhibit complete adhesive failure between the PR-420 primer and the PR-1547 polyurethane when subjected to peel testing (see figure 9). The peel strength of such samples averaged 50-60 pli. Interestingly, the NCC-coated samples in the salt water ALT bath that simulated cathodic delamination conditions routinely failed in a completely different manner. Such samples experienced complete adhesive failure between the NCC coating and the PR-420 primer (see figure 9). The peel strength for these samples averaged 1-3 pli. The failure mode of the samples from the cathodic delamination ALT matched what was seen on the actual “hull-end” connectors (see figure 5).

Fig. 9. NCC-coated monel peel samples. The upper sample was never placed into the cathodic delamination ALT; its failure mode was 100% adhesive between the PR-420 primer and the PR-1547 polyurethane. The lower sample was conditioned in the cathodic delamination ALT; its failure mode is 100% adhesive between the PR-420 primer and the NCC coating.

The observed debonding between the PR-420 primer and the NCC coating happened very rapidly after the samples were placed into the cathodic delamination ALT salt water bath. An attempt was made to obtain some information regarding the failure mechanism by making a new set of samples but pulling them from the ALT on a much quicker timescale. When these samples were peel tested, the ones that had spent the least amount of time in the ALT exhibited crude “window-frame” debonding patterns (figure 10). Thus, the debonding between

the PR-420 and the NCC coating occurred just like “standard” cathodic delamination on bare metal substrates – from the exposed edges of the bond line inwards [5]. Thus, the NCC coated monel samples appeared to be failing as a result of cathodic delamination – the very process they were designed to resist for long periods of time!

Fig. 10. NCC-coated monel coupon that had been in the cathodic delamination ALT bath for one week. The PR-420 primer was caught in the act of debonding from the NCC coating following a rough, window-frame like pattern (i.e., from the exposed edges of the coupon inwards, with the center of the coupon relatively unaffected).

After these results were obtained and confirmed through repeat testing, the Bond-Coat developer, TRI-Austin, was contacted. They immediately began an ALT with NCC-coated samples to see if they would get the same results that were being obtained at NUWC Newport. TRI-Austin confirmed that “standard” NCC-coated monel coupons failed rapidly under cathodic delamination conditions during their ALT. Thus, a bonding technology that had worked well for 10+ years now was being rapidly compromised by the conditions it should have been able to resist. Why “standard” NCC coatings no longer appear to work under cathodic delamination conditions now became a critical issue..

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The reasons why the fiber optic cable with NCC-coated connector backshells failed were now clear. Dissection of failed connectors and testing of materials used to coat and encapsulate the connectors via ALTs carried out in the laboratory, uncovered several serious, materials-related problems. Because the two ends of the cable failed for different reasons, each end will be discussed separately.

The “sensor” end of the cable had connectors made with Inconel 625 backshells so that the connectors would be galvanically compatible with titanium receptacles on the sensor itself. The sensor was also electrically isolated from the hull of the parent vessel, so the “sensor” end connectors were not cathodically polarized by the cathodic protection system used to protect the parent vessel’s hull from corrosion. Although these connectors were not cathodically polarized when deployed, their backshells were given “standard” NCC coatings. The first step in the application of a NCC coating is the deposition of a “metal interface layer” directly onto the backshell. Lacking any other official guidance, the NCC coating applicator used the same alloy (Eutectic 21021) on these connectors that was specified for the “metal interface layer” for monel substrates.

Ordinarily, the use of Eutectic 21021 for this application would not have caused any problems. NCC coatings were designed for use on hardware that was cathodically polarized and therefore subject to cathodic delamination. When a connector is cathodically polarized, the metal alloys comprising the connector are not subject to anodic corrosion reactions that would cause them to corrode/dissolve away – the cathodic current and voltage ensure the backshell metals can never participate in an anodic reaction. In the case of this particular cable, however, the backshell was not cathodically polarized when deployed, and dissimilar metals (Inconel and Eutectic 21021) were in direct contact with each other in the presence of an electrolyte (seawater). These conditions created a galvanic corrosion cell with the Inconel backshell behaving as the cathode and the NCC “metal interface layer” behaving as the anode. This resulted in the Eutectic 21021 layer being dissolved away, thereby undermining everything located above it. This was the reason why the NCC coating’s ceramic layer peeled off of the Inconel connector backshells so easily when the failed connectors were being autopsied.

The testing carried out using bare metal Inconel coupons that were not sprayed with an NCC coating verified that for this particular application in which the connector backshell was not cathodically polarized, NCC coatings were not necessary to ensure a strong and reliable bond to the polyurethane encapsulant. For the Inconel backshell connectors, the application of a NCC coating was directly responsible for the untimely connector failures. NCC coatings were designed to be used on connectors that are cathodically polarized when deployed; the use of such coatings on connectors that are not cathodically polarized may at best be a form of “overkill,” and at worst may create a serious debonding problem if the NCC coating’s metal matching layer is far enough apart from the backshell alloy on the galvanic series in seawater to trigger the initiation of a galvanic corrosion cell between the two metals.

The connector dissections and in-laboratory ALTs of NCC-coated test coupons also revealed the cause of the bonding failures seen on the connectors used on the “hull” end of the cables. Unlike the “sensor” end of the cable, the “hull” end of the cable was cathodically polarized when deployed and, therefore, its polyurethane encapsulant was subject to cathodic delamination. For these connectors, the use of NCC coatings on the connector backshells was reasonable from a materials perspective. Testing clearly revealed that these connectors failed due to cathodic delamination. The major new discovery from the current investigation was that the delamination was occurring between the NCC coating and the PR-420 primer – something that by design and past experience should not be happening! Unfortunately, the testing did not definitively reveal *why* NCC coatings were no longer working on connectors subjected to cathodic delamination conditions.

Several theories have been advanced to explain the recent poor performance of NCC coatings exposed to cathodic delamination conditions. These theories can be distilled down into three major categories: (a) there is something wrong with the PR-420 primer; (b) there is something wrong with the seal coat used on the NCC coating; and (c) conditions on new classes of ships/submarines may be harsher from a cathodic delamination perspective.

Around 1997, PRC-DeSoto stopped making PR-420 primer and tried to substitute several other primers of different chemical composition in its place. A few years after it became unavailable, PRC-DeSoto once again began making and selling a product called "PR-420 primer." It was never clear if this product was identical (from a chemical perspective) to the previous version of PR-420 primer. There were some indications that something had changed in the material (wetting issues, and an inability to obtain the same high peel strengths with polyurethanes as before); but with no definitive evidence that an undesirable formulation change had occurred, the "new" version of PR-420 was widely re-adopted for many of its former uses (including bonding polyurethane overmolds to cable connectors).

The material used for the seal coating for "standard" NCC coatings is also a concern. This material, MetcoSeal AP, has been in continuous use since the "standard" NCC coating technology was developed. It is possible that the formula for this product was changed by its manufacturer, and such a change could negatively impact the ability of PR-420 (and other primers) to bond to the NCC coating. Another issue related to this material is its chemical nature – it is a phenolic resin. Phenolic resins are known to be incompatible with high pH aqueous solutions. Cathodic delamination conditions rapidly generate a high pH environment with hydroxyl anions being generated by the reaction in equation (1) within about 250 microns of the NCC seal coat/polyurethane primer bond line when "standard" NCC coatings are applied to connector backshells.

The close proximity of the vulnerable seal coat layer to the site of generation of hydroxyl anions is worrisome for the long-term survival of NCC-coated connectors. Possibly in the past, the cathodic delamination conditions were not as severe as they are today. In the past, cathodic protection systems generally relied upon sacrificial anodes for corrosion protection, while newer vessels tend to use ICCP systems. The possibility exists that some areas of ICCP-protected hulls are sometimes "overprotected" with higher cathodic currents that would strictly be necessary. Such a situation would not negatively impact the vessel's hull, but it could increase the rate of generation of hydroxyl anions on cathodically polarized surfaces if the cathodic current was artificially driven higher. To date, no studies have been conducted to determine if some areas on more modern vessels present "harsher" environments from a cathodic delamination perspective than older vessels.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Because cathodic protection systems of various designs are in widespread use throughout the U.S. Navy and the marine industry in general, many pieces of marine hardware, including outboard cable connectors, inadvertently find themselves in locations where cathodic delamination, a process that compromises metal-to-polymer bonds, is a major concern. Research conducted at NUWC Newport discovered that a commonly used technology for preventing cathodic delamination, namely NCC coatings, no longer can be assumed to be a satisfactory "cure" for this problem. Examination of failed NCC-coated connectors and ALTs conducted on

laboratory samples indicate that "standard" NCC coatings now fail rapidly when exposed to cathodic delamination conditions. These failures are characterized by a complete adhesive debond between the NCC coating and the PR-420 primer used to adhere the PR-1547 polyurethane to the NCC coated connectors. The reasons why NCC coatings fail to function properly have not been definitively determined, but could be related to changes in primer chemistry; changes in NCC sealcoat chemistry and possibly harsher cathodic delamination conditions being present in certain spaces on newer vessels. Analysis of failed cables with NCC coatings also revealed a potential danger caused by the use of these coatings on certain connectors not subject to cathodic debonding conditions. In particular, the use of the NCC metal interface layer alloy Eutectic 21021 on connector backshells comprised of Inconel can be problematic. Inconel and Eutectic 21021 are galvanically incompatible with each other in seawater. If Eutectic 21021 is used as the metal matching layer for bonding NCC to an inconel backshell, a galvanic corrosion cell will rapidly develop once the connector is exposed to seawater. The Eutectic 21021 will be preferentially dissolved away, thereby undermining the NCC layer and anything bonded to it. This example re-enforces the notion that NCC coatings should not necessarily be required for connectors that are not subjected to cathodic delamination conditions. At best, the result will be an un-necessary additional expense for the cable, and at worst, it could trigger a catastrophic debonding failure between the connector backshell and its polyurethane encapsulant.

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